

**SOME METHODS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES, THEIR
FAILS, ALSO WAY OF USING IT**

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Annotation. The article is about methods of learning foreign languages. Such kinds of methods: Listening, reading, speaking, and learning new words. This paragraph answers some questions, exactly: How use these ways? Why do people have failings during using these techniques? Also, the views and opinions of many scientists on the definition of the methodologies of learning foreign languages are commented on.

Keywords: listening, lyrics, speech, communication, reading, fairy tale, news, learning new words.

Аннотация: Статья о методах изучения иностранных языков. Такие методы как: Слушание, чтение, разговорная речь и изучение новых слов. Этот параграф ответит на вопросы, а именно: Как использовать эти способы? Почему люди имеют неудачи в процессе использования этих методов? Также комментируется взгляды и мнения многих ученых по поводу определения методики изучения иностранных языков.

Ключевые слова: аудирование, лирика, речь, общение, чтение, сказка, новость, изучение новых слов.

After knowing all letters, everybody starts slowly learning new words. And in this time people begin making a lot of misapprehensions. Cause of it, firstly everyone begins learning with academic or hard words. Secondly, start with words that they do not use in real life. In the other hand, human learns a lot without using at present. So, it is easy to say mistakes. But how to learn new words? You will ask. In the beginning start with words, that you use every day. It can be: stationary (pen, pencil, notebook, book and etc.), kitchen utensils (pan, spoon, fork and others). But not learn much in a day. Fundamental, learn less and use more, after this kind of learning you will have more effects. “The main thing is not quantity, but quality “— says Duman Kazhybek [2]. After knowing simple words start learning a little harder vocabulary.

Reading fairy tales help you learn elementary words. In this way you start, not only learning new words and reading, although speaking. When you read fables your imagination work faster. It helps you to try say your feelings about story.

But not forget paraphrase your tale in your new foreign language.” The fairy tale promotes the development of creative abilities of students, creates an emotionally positive atmosphere of cooperation. It known that at the initial stage of learning language there are some restrictions in the manifestation of speech activity associated with the lack of speech and language tools. During lessons it is necessary to stimulate speech activity so that it was as much as possible motivated, which means that the younger students must be caused by the need to understand the statement perceived by hearing, to express their attitude towards what is happening” -says Sharipova Charos Akbarovna (Teacher at School № 263) [3]. By reading and telling stories you will study only easily process of your success.

Start more communicating with each other, it also helps with ease describe your opinions. If you have some problems in your speech, try to sing songs with lyrics. It will be funny, if you start your listening with rap. Do not use this way, because it is so hard. Start with the simple lyrics. For example: pop-music. This type of music is not as fast as possible, that’s why it is good way for vocalizing. Additionally, choose more and more difficult notes, step by step. But during finding music ask your teacher or a partner who knows this language, because there are so many defects. That’s why ask person who knows tongue before choosing note. But if you not fan of listening music, hark news, it is better than listening to chime. News help you to speak literary. Unfortunately, this is harder way, but so successful. You should try, and you will see results as fast as possible. Listen to news do not mean that you need hear one time. You should listen it until you understand meaning. Also, it will be better if you dictate news. “There are a couple of habits to get into which will help you master active learning. It requires practice and it is unlikely you will be able to do it all the time but to start you will need to:

- Concentrate on what is being said - don’t be distracted and don’t formulate a response early
- Show that you are engaged – look at the person speaking, nod occasionally to show that you’re listening
- Wait for the speaker to finish speaking before asking questions and don’t interrupt with a response
- Summarize your understanding if something large or complicated has been explained” - says science [1].

Nowadays, there are many different ways to learn English. Each has its own merits and gives positive results. Some methods recommended for teaching

schoolchildren. However, there is a very interesting option that is well-received by both adults and children. You can probably guess that English fairy tales are the most effective tool by which language learning becomes an exciting experience. This aspect is especially appreciated by the children's audience. Because the goal of teaching English as English is to help students communicate fluently in the target language, teachers must provide authentic language use patterns for each level and age. To hit the target, we must focus not only on linguistics but also on literary and cultural elements. Since fairy tales offer these elements, they are very useful in English language teaching programs, especially for younger students. It should be borne in mind that the selection of fairy tales should be carried out taking into account the purpose of the course, the age of the students, and the content of the story. Because each learning situation is unique, the use of each story fragment varies from class to class and teacher to teacher. However, the use of fairy tales in elementary English courses as literary works, as a rule, improves communicative competence and provides a springboard for the development of critical thinking and aesthetic perception. This is beneficial for many benefits such as cultural enrichment, language development, higher order thinking, and more. To achieve the next goal, great importance is attached to the methodology and strategies for teaching English with the help of fairy tales.

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3. THE ROLE OF FAIRY TALES IN THE TEACHING OF ENGLISH – тема научной статьи по языкознанию и литературоведению читайте бесплатно текст научно-исследовательской работы в электронной библиотеке КиберЛенинка (cyberleninka.ru)

